

TAILORED STIFFNESS OF BALSA SANDWICH CORE MATERIAL

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SUMMARY

A concept for tailoring the stiffness properties of balsa core material to sandwich structures is presented. The concept is modeled using basic laminate theory to predict the shear stiffness with respect to a sandwich beam. This is subsequently validated through experiments. A substantial increase in the shear stiffness is demonstrated.

Keywords: Sandwich, core material, balsa, stiffness tailoring, shear modulus

INTRODUCTION

Balsa wood is frequently used for core material in sandwich structures, due to the favorable stiffness/weight ratio. Descriptions of the general use of balsa wood in sandwich structures may be found in standard handbooks, such as [1] by Zenkert. It is usually oriented with the grain-direction normal to the extension plane of a sandwich panel – one reason for this is retardation of decomposition due to moisture in case of a face-sheet puncture. Also, the high axial (along the grain) stiffness of balsa wood improves the resistance of the sandwich panel to local indentations and face-sheet wrinkling and dimpling. In a recent study by Tagarielli et al. [2], the axial compression properties were shown to be highly strain-rate sensitive, providing a significant increase in dynamic strength compared to the quasi-static behavior. Furthermore, the study demonstrated, in agreement with several previous studies, that the axial compressive strength properties are clearly superior to those of PVC foams of comparable densities. However, the orientation of the axial direction transverse to the sandwich panel plane gives a poor utilization of the orthotropic properties of the wood with respect to the transfer of transverse (shear) force through the core, and makes the core prone to sudden transverse splitting. A concept for improving the stiffness using balsa elements was presented by Bekisli and Grenestedt [3]. This provided an improved shear stiffness in two primary transverse planes, but required elaborate machining of the balsa elements.

Simplified Concept

The concept presented here provides an improvement of the shear properties in only one transverse plane, but is straightforward and economically feasible. The principle is illustrated in figures 1 and 2. Thin plates (thickness $b = 5$ mm in the present study) of

balsa wood are cut at an angle α to the grain direction. In the present examination, three values have been investigated, $\alpha = 90^\circ, 67.5^\circ, 45^\circ$, as indicated in figure 1.

Figure 1: Balsa elements at different plane-to-grain angles α .

Subsequent cuts separated a distance H_c corresponding to the desired core material thickness. The pre-cut elements are then stacked at alternating angles $\pm \alpha$ to provide a core beam or plate. The stacking sequence may be arbitrary, but in the present study, angles α are kept constant in any given specimen or model as exemplified in figure 2.

Figure 2: Stacking of balsa elements, height H_c and width b at alternating angles $\pm \alpha$.

PREDICTION OF SHEAR STIFFNESS

Through the use of classical (plane) laminate theory, the effective shear modulus may be calculated for a stacked balsa core at a given stacking sequence. Initially, the elementary properties of the balsa wood in the principal material coordinates (axial, radial and tangential for wooden materials) must be measured or estimated through

empirical formulas. In the present case, results from the lap shear tests are used in conjunction with estimated values based on the measured balsa density. Properties in the radial and tangential directions are, by necessity, averaged.

Laminate theory requires constitutive data related to the principal directions of orthotropy in the individual plies; in the present case, this corresponds to

- the axial modulus of elasticity $E_{11} \left(\cong \frac{\rho}{\rho_s} \cdot E_s \right)$
- the transverse modulus $E_{22} \left(\cong C \cdot \left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_s} \right)^3 \cdot E_s \right)$, $C = 0.54 - 0.8$
- the Poisson's ratios ν_{12} and ν_{21} (interdependent, $\nu_{12} = 0.23-0.49$)
- the shear modulus $G_{66} \left(\cong 0.074 \frac{\rho}{\rho_s} \cdot E_s \right)$

where the index notation corresponds to the notation typically used in classical laminate theory. In parenthesis above are given the suggestions outlined by Gibson and Ashby [4]. Following these, with

$$\rho = 129 \text{ kg/m}^3 \text{ (measured from the specific balsa wood)}$$

$$\rho_s = 1500 \text{ kg/m}^3 \text{ (cell wall density, according to [4])}$$

$$E_s = 35 \text{ GPa (axial cell wall modulus, according to [4])}$$

one obtains

$$E_{11} = 3010 \text{ MPa}, E_{22} = 15 \text{ MPa (12 - 18 MPa)}, G_{66} = 223 \text{ Mpa}, \nu_{12} = 0.33 \text{ (0.23-0.49)}$$

Clearly, the dominant factors are E_{11} and G_{66} . Using classical laminate theory, the dependence of the apparent shear modulus G_{xy} on the angle α is shown in figure 9.

The value obtained for E_{22} seems unrealistically low, and direct measurements on the 5 mm thick balsa plates was impractical. Therefore, measurements were performed on a larger plank of balsa wood. For this specimen, the density was 78 kg/m^3 , and the primary extensional moduli were measured:

$E_{11} = 1630 \text{ MPa}$ (which is in reasonably good agreement with the corresponding predicted value of 1820 MPa). The predicted value for a density $\rho = 129 \text{ kg/m}^3$ is reduced correspondingly, giving $E_{11} = 2700 \text{ MPa}$.

$E_{22} = 26.5 \text{ MPa}$ (which is in poor agreement with the predicted range of 2.66 to 3.94 MPa). Choosing instead an exponent $n = 2.3$ rather than 3 , the predicted range of E_{22} becomes 21.1 MPa to 31.2 MPa for a density of 78 kg/m^3 . For the density $\rho = 129 \text{ kg/m}^3$, the predicted value then becomes $E_{22} = 83 \text{ MPa}$ ($67 - 99 \text{ MPa}$), which is used subsequently.

Results for the laminate theory predictions are given in the comparison in figure 9 later in this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

For verification of the predicted shear stiffness, simple lap shear experiments and 3-point sandwich beam bending experiments were conducted.

Preparation of Test Specimens

In the present investigation, the parameters

$$H_c = 20 \text{ mm}$$

$$b = 5 \text{ mm}$$

were kept constant. The specimens used for the experimental verifications invariably consisted of six layers with a stacking sequence of $[\pm \alpha]_3$. For specimens where $\alpha \neq 90^\circ$, this introduces a small amount of shear/twist coupling, which is ignored in the following.

For manufacture of a specimen, strips of balsa wood was cut at the appropriate angle from 5 mm thick plates of balsa wood, with a strip width slightly larger than the final core height (22 mm for a final core height $H_c = 20$ mm). The six layers for a given specimen were then bonded together using a PVA wood glue (Akzo Nobel, Cascol 3301). The glue was diluted with water (1:1 by volume), for facilitation of the glue application (using a painting brush). After adhesion, the specimens were left to dry at room temperature for one week, whereupon the specimens were trimmed to the final height.

Face sheets for sandwich beam specimens were cut from mild steel plate:

$$\text{Thickness } t_f = 1 \text{ mm, width } B = 6b = 30 \text{ mm, modulus } E_f = 210 \text{ Gpa}$$

Immediately prior to bonding of the face sheets to the core, the face sheets were lightly bead-blasted and degreased using acetone. For bonding sandwich face sheets or lap shear bars to the core specimens, an epoxy adhesive (Araldite 2011) was used. The specimens were kept under pressure for 24 hours after adhesive assembly, then left to harden for another 24 hours, i.e. 48 hours at room temperature.

Lap shear experiments

The shear stiffness for two configurations ($\alpha = 90^\circ, 45^\circ$) was investigated using a standard lap shear test. The experimental setup is shown in figure 3.

Fig. 3: Lap shear test setup. The parts are: a – steel shear bars, b – shear specimen

In figure 3, the test setup is shown with an $\alpha = 45^\circ$ specimen. The small angle between the specimen extension direction and the line of action of the forces F is ignored. A high-sensitivity clip gauge measures the relative motion between the steel shear bars.

The specimen dimensions were: length $L = 240$ mm, width $B = 30$ mm, height $H_c = 20$ mm

One weakness of the lap shear tests, as the one illustrated in figure 3, is that a uniform shear stress over the length of the specimen cannot be fulfilled near the free edges of the specimen. In the present case, the balsa core material is highly orthotropic, with the direction of maximum stiffness of the individual core-layer indicated by the angle α , and a specimen length detriment has been introduced, according to figure 4.

Fig. 4: Determination of length detriment according to the specimen grain direction, where the shaded area d is ignored for the purpose of assessing the shear stiffness G_{xy} .

Therefore, referring to figure 4, an area d at each end of the specimen is considered ineffective for transferring the shear stress in the specimen. The length of the specimen is, for the purpose of calculating the shear stress, reduced correspondingly (by 20 mm for the $\alpha = 45^\circ$; no reduction for $\alpha = 90^\circ$), producing representative lengths:

$$L_{rep}(\alpha = 45^\circ) = 220 \text{ mm}$$

$$L_{rep}(\alpha = 90^\circ) = 240 \text{ mm}$$

The results of the lap shear tests are shown in figure 5.

Lap shear test results

Fig. 5: Shear stress/strain curves for specimens with $\alpha = 90^\circ$ and 45° .

Calculation of the effective shear modulus is done as follows:

$$\tau = G_{xy} \cdot \gamma = \frac{F}{L_{rep} \cdot B} \Rightarrow G_{xy} = \frac{F}{L_{rep} \cdot B \cdot \gamma}$$

where: F : shear force (see figure X), L_{rep} : representative length, as discussed above,

B : specimen width, γ : shear strain

The shear strain γ is, for small deformations, calculated by

$$\gamma = \Delta / H_c$$

where D : lap shear plate displacement (as measured using clip gauges, see figure 4)

H_c : specimen height

The corresponding effective shear moduli, derived from the lap shear experiments as the limit secant moduli for $\gamma \rightarrow 0$, were: $G_{xy}(\alpha = 45^\circ) = 655 \text{ Mpa}$, $G_{xy}(\alpha = 90^\circ) = 134 \text{ Mpa}$

Sandwich beam experiments

As mentioned above, the free edges of the lap shear test specimens introduce a zone of nonuniform shear stress. For compensation, the representative length of the specimen was reduced according to the orthotropic characteristics of the specimen. For a separate verification of the core properties, sandwich beam specimens subjected to symmetrical 3-point bending were studied, using stacked balsa core at three different angles ($\alpha = 90^\circ, 67.5^\circ, 45^\circ$). The beam geometry is shown in figure 6.

Fig. 6: Sandwich beam specimen. $L = 300 \text{ mm}$, $L_1 = 130 \text{ mm}$, $L_{ins} = 20 \text{ mm}$, $B = 30 \text{ mm}$, $H_c = 20 \text{ mm}$, $t_f = 1 \text{ mm}$

The test was performed in a 20 kN test machine with the specimen supported on a moving crosshead, as shown in figure 7.

Fig. 7: Closeup picture of 3-point sandwich beam bending test, showing:
a: load cell, b: central loading tup, c: sandwich beam specimen with load introduction inserts at the endpoints and the middle, d: support rollers, e: crosshead

Prior to the recorded test results (see below), the specimens were loaded moderately (to 500 N) and unloaded to verify the specimen / support fit. In figure 8, the force/displacement relations for six tests are shown.

Fig. 8: Force / deflection curves for three-point sandwich beam bending tests. $F_{\alpha, \#}$ indicates the $\#$ th test of a specimen with core angle α .

In the first three tests ($\# = 1$) in figure 8, the specimens were moderately loaded to provide data for the specimen compliances. In the second three tests ($\# = 2$), the specimens were loaded to failure.

Of immediate interest, the failure strength varies only moderately between the three specimens, with a nominal failure shear stress τ_{fail} between 3.8 and 4.2 MPa. However, all three failed specimens exhibited failure in the interface between the core and the face-sheets, where the interface bond rather than the core strength has been the determining factor. As the present investigation deals primarily with the shear stiffness, this is of secondary importance.

Using first order shear deformation theory (FOSDT), the measured specimen compliance was compared with a calculated compliance, with the shear stiffness G_{xy} of the core material as the single unknown quantity.

The apparent shear stiffnesses were

$$G_{xy} (\alpha = 45^\circ) = 670 \text{ Mpa}, G_{xy} (\alpha = 67.5^\circ) = 350 \text{ Mpa}, G_{xy} (\alpha = 90^\circ) = 147 \text{ Mpa}$$

COMPARISON OF RESULTS

In figure 9, predicted values of the apparent shear modulus G_{xy} are presented alongside the values inferred from the experiments, corresponding to the test specimen range of angles α .

Fig. 9: Comparison of apparent shear modulus $G_{xy}(\alpha)$ found by: laminate theory with material properties estimated according to [4](G&A), lap shear test, sandwich beam 3-point bending test and laminate theory using measured or directly extrapolated material parameters

When using base orthotropic properties predicted directly according to [4], the level of shear stiffness is substantially and consistently higher than the measured values.

Instead, the values measured directly or extrapolated from measured data may be used:

$$E_{11} = 2700 \text{ MPa}, E_{22} = 83 \text{ MPa}, G_{66} = 134 \text{ Mpa}, \nu_{12} = 0.33 (0.23-0.49)$$

and one obtains a much better agreement.

At $\alpha = 90^\circ$, where the direct result for the lap shear test was used as input for the laminate theory model, the agreement between theory and experimental data must obviously be good. In the intermediate range, specifically comparing the result from 3-point sandwich beam bending at $\alpha = 67.5^\circ$ with the prediction from laminate theory, the agreement is less convincing, but still within reasonable limits.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The results of the modeling and measurements are not in full agreement – one reason may be found in the Love-Kirchoff assumptions of classical laminate theory which state that deformation-, strain- and stress-effects out of the stacking plane may be ignored. With the thickness ($b = 5 \text{ mm}$) and the relative softness of the balsa core “plies”, these assumptions may not permit an adequate description of the deformation state.

Applying First-Order Shear Deformation Theory (FOSDT) for extracting the shear modulus in the 3-point bending tests, the shear stress distribution was assumed uniform across the core. Furthermore, the assumptions of a simple FOSDT are not properly satisfied in the transition region between steel inserts and balsa core; the face-sheet shear stiffness contribution can not be ignored completely. However, this would logically indicate a higher combined shear stiffness, whereas the actual result is somewhat lower than predicted.

The method of manufacture involved diluted PVA glue. It may be that the exposure to excess moisture degraded the mechanical properties of the balsa wood (see e.g. [5]). However, as the balsa wood is relatively open for diffusion and was stored in a dry room at room temperature for one week after core manufacture, this is deemed unlikely.

The measured apparent shear stiffnesses were 134-147 MPa for $\alpha = 90^\circ$, 350 MPa for $\alpha = 67.5^\circ$ and 655-670 MPa for $\alpha = 45^\circ$, indicating an approximately fourfold increase in shear stiffness. This was adequately supported by simple modeling. Manufacture can be automated without disproportionately large waste or time consumption. The compressional stiffness will be somewhat compromised, compared to a 90° grain-to-plane angle.

The fracture morphology has not been the primary issue of the present investigation, but studies of the failed specimens indicate that stacking at alternating angles $\pm \alpha$ increases the resilience, as the fibres of crossing layers of balsa core tend to bridge across transverse core cracks.

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